

Evaluating Large Language Models in Interaction with Open Government Data

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) exhibit great abilities in understanding and generating natural language. Open Government Data (OGD) are datasets that while are available to the public, their linked structure makes it difficult to access. Large language models can significantly enhance access to linked open government data by enabling users to interact with OGD portals using natural language. This study examines the use of LLMs to interact with open government linked data effectively and efficiently. Based on the QB vocabulary, we develop a framework that formulates the task. A set of 20 questions is developed to assess the capabilities of LLMs to execute OGD-related tasks. We propose a simple system in which LLMs interact semi-automatically with OGD. Our findings indicate that smaller and quantized versions of popular LLMs are capable of effectively managing these tasks, with Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct-bnb-4bit identified as the most effective model. This paper aims to promote further interest in systems that enhance Open Government Data portals and improve public access to open data.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **E-government**; • **Information systems** → **Information systems applications**; **Information retrieval**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Natural language processing**.

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Keywords

large language models, open government data, linked data, natural language processing

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1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have proven to be highly effective in a variety of settings [12, 31, 34]. New methods for locating and extracting information from unstructured natural language have been sparked by their advantages. Researchers are increasingly exploring how LLMs can be applied to various Information Extraction (IE) tasks. [9, 10]. Additionally, recent works have shown the outstanding generalization of LLMs to not only learn from IE training data through fine-tuning [37], but also extract information in few-shot scenarios relying solely on in-context examples or pure instructions [2, 29, 30, 32, 35].

Open Government Data (OGD) provides a way to make information widely accessible to the public. When released as linked data based on the QB Vocabulary¹, OGD offers the additional advantage of semantically structured content, enabling sophisticated queries that facilitate the retrieval of accurate and up-to-date information. Combining linked OGD with AI technologies can yield interesting results [17]. Specifically, LLMs' ability to understand and produce natural language can be used to utilise massive amounts of OGD and develop effective systems that benefit the general public. (e.g. [20, 23]).

In this study, we explore the utilization of Large Language Models (LLMs) to effectively and efficiently interact with linked OGD.

¹<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-data-cube/>

Towards this direction, a framework is synthesized that, based on the structure of linked OGD specified by the QB Vocabulary (e.g., measures, dimensions, etc.), defines the parameters of the complexity of questions applicable to linked OGD. Based on the framework, a set of 20 questions related to datasets available on the Scottish Open Statistics Portal² is created and organized into four categories. Finally, a simple system is implemented in which LLMs interact semi-autonomously with the portal to answer the questions. Four LLMs, namely Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct-bnb-4bit, mistral-7b-instruct-v0.3-bnb-4bit, gemma-2-9b-bnb-4bit, and all-MiniLM-L6-v2 are evaluated based on the framework.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides background knowledge regarding OGD and LLMs. In section 3 we describe our research approach. In section 4 we define the framework and formulate the task, while in section 5 we describe how the set of questions is created. In section 6 we are presenting the architecture and the workflow of the system interacting with the portal. We evaluate the performance of the LLMs and present significant observations in section 7. Discussion and conclusions, including future work, are presented in Section 8.

2 Background

2.1 Linked Open Government Data

Open Government Data (OGD) refers to the information collected, produced, or paid by the public authorities and made freely available for reuse for any purpose. In the recent decade, the act of making government data publicly available is a political priority, with multiple purposes varying from improving efficiency of public administrations, economic growth and transparency to wider social welfare. OGD are accessible through official data portals of governments. Despite the numerous benefits of OGD, its accessibility remains limited due to several key challenges [33]. Government bodies often face institutional barriers, such as legal restrictions and limited capacity, which hinder the effective collection and sharing of data. Additionally, technical issues related to outdated data portals and lack of system functionality create barriers for users trying to access OGD. Even when data can be accessed, citizens and organizations may struggle to use it effectively, due to insufficient IT resources or data available to them needs. Because it is not straightforward to use, these limitations prevent OGD from realizing its full potential, limiting its impact boundary despite its great benefits.

Many official OGD portals are publishing data as linked data, in order to further unlock their potential. Linked data are based on the Semantic Web philosophy, and they primarily involve publishing structured data using the W3C Resource Description Framework (RDF) standard. The main RDF vocabulary for describing statistical data is the Data Cube Vocabulary (QB) [6]. This is a W3C standard that models statistical information as data cubes. These data cubes include a set of dimensions defining the context of dataset observations (e.g. Reference Area, Reference Period), measures (qb:MeasureProperty) representing the phenomena being observed, and attributes (qb:AttributeProperty) that convey structural metadata like units of measurement. While linked facts

offer large benefits—which include facilitating statistics integration and enabling analytics throughout previously isolated datasets [15, 21]—they introduce an additional technical barrier for users. To effectively access and utilize linked data, users must know how to query these data forms, which can be challenging without specialized knowledge or tools.

The OGD from the Scottish Open Statistics Portal currently hosts 289 datasets covering various social and economical aspects of Scotland. Users can access the data portal in several ways to explore and obtain data. They can view data presented as tables, maps, or charts and have the option to download it in formats like HTML, JSON, or CSV. Alternatively, the portal provides a SPARQL endpoint³ that allows users to submit flexible queries to retrieve the data as linked data.

2.2 Large Language Models

Large language models or LLMs from small and beyond, are trainable, Artificial Intelligence models used for natural language tasks in massive datasets. Since the introduction of the transformative transformer architecture [7, 25] and the attention mechanism [28], the development of LLMs has progressed rapidly. These innovations have enabled models to capture contextual information in a bidirectional manner, significantly enhancing their performance and enabling the creation of sophisticated systems. LLMs are now capable of handling a wide range of tasks, from text classification [11] and named entity recognition [22] to summarization [18] and translation [39]. However, their greatest strength lies in their ability to understand and generate human-like text [5], opening up numerous possibilities for diverse applications.

Models with such capabilities are becoming more and more available to the public. AI as-a-service providers such as OpenAI gives easy access to their powerful GPT [38] LLM family models (GPT-3.5 [36], GPT-4 [1]). Open source models are now providing comparable capabilities to the private ones. The Llama LLM family (Llama [1], Llama2 [27] and Llama3 [8]) released by Meta, the Mistral LLM family (Mistral 7B [13]) released by Mistral AI and the Gemma LLM family [26, 26] released by Google are only some examples of such open source models. Those models are widely available, either through APIs or locally hosted solutions, offer new ways to manipulate natural language textual information.

The massive potential of LLMs, mentioned previously, stems from the generative models' ability to adapt to a wide range of natural language tasks that they did not initially train on through instruction and example based learning that often rivals fine tuning approaches [4]. Specifically, it is shown that in-context instruction learning can not only boost the zero-shot task generalization performance of pretrained but also of instruction-fine-tuned models [37]. Through instruction and example based learning, conversational LLMs are taught how to perform new, unseen tasks as humans would. By understanding the new natural language task presented in a descriptive manner, the LLM is usually able to accomplish it with high performance. Examples of such human-oriented instruction [19] applications include but are not limited to summarization [3], text classification [24] and named entity recognition [29]; tasks

²<https://statistics.gov.scot/home>

³<https://statistics.gov.scot/sparql>

that were previously performed by dedicated models specifically trained or fine-tuned for such purposes.

3 Research Approach

Answering questions based on linked data involves translating user input into a SPARQL query and generating a natural language response based on the retrieved data. To better understand the challenges of this process we define a framework derived from the Data Cube vocabulary (QB) and the cube components. Using this framework, we define a set of parameters that characterise the challenges of possible questions, posed to statistical datasets. Using these parameters, we then create a set of 20 questions divided into 4 categories. Each category is intended to present distinct challenges, without implying that one is inherently more difficult than the others.

We develop a basic system in which LLMs interact quasi - autonomously with the SPARQL endpoint of the Scottish statistical data portal, allowing end users to query statistical information in natural language rather than SPARQL queries. Such systems have heavily depended on the capabilities of strong closed-source LLMs, attempting to complete the same task with a single prompt that includes all important context [20]. We design our system differently by breaking the question-answering process into simpler tasks. This strategy allows us to use and evaluate smaller language models that are unable to handle large prompts with complicated information.

We evaluate the LLMs within our system based not only on their ability to generate the final answer to the user’s question but also on their performance in the subtasks defined by our architecture. The final answers are assessed by a human evaluator, while the performance in subtasks is evaluated against predefined ground truth cases.

4 Framework

A statistical dataset, S , is a set of observed values organized along a group of dimensions, accompanied by associated metadata. The Data Cube vocabulary (QB) enables such information to be represented using the RDF standard and published in accordance with the principles of linked data. We can think of the statistical data set as a multi-dimensional space, or hypercube (referred to as a cube). A cube is organised according to a set of dimensions, D , and measures, M , collectively referred to as components. A question to a statistical dataset serves as a filter, specifying a subset of dimensions, d , and measures, m . The user expects a response in natural language, based on the dataset slice, s . Accordingly, we define two tasks: retrieving the dataset slice and formatting a human readable response based on its information.

SPARQL is used to obtain information from linked data. A subset of dimensions and measures is arranged into a SPARQL query, Q , that returns the appropriate dataset slice. Having an information need in natural language, we first extract all the referenced dimensions and measures, and then we plug them into a template to create a SPARQL query. Creating a simple SPARQL query template is straightforward. Our focus is on developing a function F that extracts and returns the subset of dimensions and measures.

The dataset slice is obtained in JSON format and a function G translates it to natural language. The volume of the retrieved

information is analogous to the number of unspecified dimensions and measures in the query. If the number of supplied dimensions and measures is lower, then a larger dataset slice is retrieved which increases the difficulty of function G .

Based on this, we define a set of parameters to characterize the complexity of the questions posed to a statistical dataset. These parameters are, *the number of dimensions in the dataset*, *the number of dimensions and measures specified in the question*, and *the number of datasets required to retrieve the information necessary to answer the question*. We identify four subtasks that are involved in using natural language to interact with linked data based on the prior investigation. *Measure Selection*, *Dimension Value Extraction*, and *Dataset Selection* tasks are all included in function F . Since the query template is explicitly created and filled out with values from the F function, there is no special task set for the Q function. Lastly, the *Final Response Generation* task is part of function G . In addition to enhancing system design, identifying these tasks offers stepping stones to assess LLM performance after the final response is generated.

$$\begin{aligned} F(\{D, M\}) &= \{d, m\}, \quad \{d, m\} \subseteq \{D, M\} \\ S &= (D, M), \quad Q(S) = s = (d, m) \\ G(s) &= \text{final_response} \end{aligned}$$

5 Set of questions

Based on the parameters and subtasks defined by our framework we create a set of 20 questions organized in 4 categories. The questions are based on the components of the statistical datasets available in the Scottish open statistical portal. As of October 7, 2024, the portal includes 289 datasets. The data on this portal are modeled as data cubes, each comprising a set of dimensions, measures, and attributes that define specific observations. Using the codelists of these datasets, we retrieve the dimensions and measures associated with each one. With this information we can select datasets with specific number of dimensions and measures and thus formulate questions that reference a particular number of those dimensions and measures.

The 4 question categories are not organized in a structure of progressive complexity. Rather, each category includes questions that test different aspects of the task, thus testing different abilities of LLMs. These categories occur from tuning the parameters described in our framework. For example we can focus on testing the ability of LLMs to select the appropriate datasets for each question. For this we change the parameter *Number of datasets involved* and keep the rest at their default value. Accordingly, if we want to test the capabilities of LLMs regarding the correct extraction of values for every dimension, we change the *Number of dimension values mentioned in the question* and keep the rest at their default value. Combining parameters can also lead to interesting experimentation set ups. For example, we can change the *Number of dimension values mentioned in the question* and *Number of dimension values unspecified by the question* parameters to examine if LLMs can not only extract the correct value per dimension, but also handle the dimensions for which no value is provided in the question.

Each dataset selection in the Scottish statistical portal addresses a specific topic related to Scotland’s social and economic aspects.

Thus each questions covers the specific topic of the dataset and describes a complete information need about the topic. Multiple datasets are of similar topics, so it is realistic to assume that questions will arise whose information needs are covered by two or more datasets. There are also datasets comprised of multiple dimensions and measures. Realistic questions mention different numbers of those components. To account for these scenarios, we have formulated our questions to represent multiple cases, ranging from those that mention all available dimensions and measures to those that reference only one.

The categories and the questions we create are presented in Table 1. The first category includes questions derived from datasets with one measure and two dimensions available, with values specified in the question for both. The second category consists of questions drawn from datasets with multiple measures available. The questions specify also multiple measures and a value for each available dimension. The third category has questions derived from datasets with one measure and multiple dimensions available. These questions do not specify a value for each available dimension. Finally, the fourth category consists of questions which are based on two datasets, specify one or two measures and multiple dimensions.

6 Question-answering system

The system is composed of seven components and implements the three functions, (F, Q, G) , described in our framework. It offers basic capabilities to process user input, transform it into a SPARQL query, and interact with the portal’s SPARQL endpoint to retrieve the requested data. Finally, it generates a natural language response for the user, based on the retrieved data. An LLM is part of the system and handles different tasks between components.

The *Embedding Generation* component is responsible to encode any natural language information, into the embedding space. At the core of this component lays the encoder of a selected LLM. The data processed on this component are the user’s input and the descriptions of the datasets with their comments. The embeddings are stored in a simple table along with the corresponding dataset description and comments. The *Retrieval* component implements the functionality of retrieving the most suitable dataset to the question. It calculates the similarity of the question embeddings against the stored embeddings of the datasets. The similarity metric used is the cosine distance of the two vectors, shown below,

$$\text{CosineDistance}(\theta) = 1 - \frac{\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\|\mathbf{A}\|_2 \|\mathbf{B}\|_2}$$

where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are two vectors in the embedding space, and θ is the angle between them.

The *Prompt Generation* component is responsible to generate, modify and augment the prompts that later will be supplied to next components. Such prompts are comprised of instructions and data, accompanied with examples to further enhance the accuracy of the response. The *Portal Communication* component is responsible for transmitting and receiving information to and from the SPARQL endpoint of the Scottish Open Statistical Portal. We use this endpoint not only to retrieve the final data but also to obtain additional information, such as the available dimension labels for each dataset and the corresponding values for each dimension label. The *Query*

Construction component utilizes the dimensions and measures extracted from different processes and creates the final SPARQL query based on a query template. The *Extraction and response generation* component plays a double role. First it is responsible for extracting information from the user’s input based on the available measures and dimensions for every dataset. Additionally it is responsible of generating the final response to the user. At the core of this component lies the selected LLM.

Figure 1: Components of the designed system and their interactions

The connections and interactions of the components depicted in Figure 1 can be summarized as follows: The user provides the initial natural language question as input. The LLM of the *Extraction and generation* component is responsible for extracting the dimensions and measures mentioned in the question. At the same time, the *Embedding generation* and *Retriever* component work in tandem to embed the user’s question and retrieve the most suitable datasets. The extracted dimensions and values along with the datasets URL are used by the *Query generation* component to construct the SPARQL query which then is sent to the SPARQL portal. The retrieved dataset slice is supplied to the *Extraction and generation* component which produces the final response in natural language. The final answer is presented to the user.

The *Extraction and Generation* component responds in JSON format when it is asked to determine the dimensions and measures of the question. This makes it straightforward to parse the response and match each extracted value to its corresponding label. The values available for each dimension and measure are predefined for each dataset and can be accessed through the SPARQL endpoint. Some dimension or measure values mentioned in the query might be paraphrased. Using the *Retriever* component, we compute the cosine similarity between the retrieved values and those available for the dataset, utilizing the *Retriever* component. The complete workflow of the system is illustrated in Figure 2.

7 Evaluation

The results reveal that certain tasks were relatively simpler, while others more challenging for the Large Language Models (LLMs). Below, we present the results for the *Dataset Selection* and *Dimension Value Extraction* tasks in graphical form. The findings for the *Measure Selection* task, however, are straightforward. All tested LLMs

Question ID	Question
Q1.A	How many HMO licenses were in force in Dundee City in 2011? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/hmo-licences
Q1.B	How much urban vacant land was there in East Ayrshire in 2016? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/vacant-derelict-land
Q1.C	In 2014, how many Scottish Child Payment applications were denied for individuals aged 25-50 in Scotland? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/scottish-child-payment-caseload
Q1.D	What was the percentage of 25-50 year old males in Scotland who were regular smokers in 2014, within the 1st SIMD quintile (most deprived)? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/smoking-prevalence-and-deprivation-salsus
Q1.E	In 2014, what was the number of business stocks in the manufacturing sector (SIC 07 Section C) within the registered private sector, employing 100-399 employees, located in large urban areas of Scotland? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/business-stocks-and-sites-by-urban-rural-classification
Q2.A	In Scotland in 2014, what was the amount and ratio of incidents of domestic abuse recorded per 10,000 population? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/domestic-abuse-recorded-by-the-police-number-of-incidents-and-rates
Q2.B	In Scotland in 2014, what were the index value and annual growth rate of goods and services produced in the construction sector (Section F)? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/gross-domestic-product-annual-output-by-industry
Q2.C	In Scotland in 2014, what were the index, quarter-on-quarter compared to a year ago (q-on-q year ago), and quarter-on-quarter (q-on-q) values for output per job as a measure of productivity? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/labour-productivity-quarterly
Q2.D	In Scotland in 2014, what were the count, ratio, 95% upper confidence limit, and 95% lower confidence limit for unemployment model-based estimates across all industry sectors? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/unemployment-model-based-estimates
Q2.E	In Scotland in 2014, what were the median, mean, lower quartile, and upper quartile values of residential property transactions? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/house-sales-prices
Q3.A	How many HMO licenses were in force in Dundee City? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/hmo-licences
Q3.B	How much vacant urban land was there in East Ayrshire in 2016? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/vacant-derelict-land
Q3.C	What percent of children were classed as clinically overweight in Scotland? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/p1-BMI-clinical
Q3.D	How many VAT/PAYE registered operating sites were in Scotland in 2018? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/business-stocks-and-sites-by-region-of-ownership
Q3.E	In Scotland in 2014, what was the number of children living under poverty in private rented accommodation, with families of three children, and with two adults working? Reference dataset: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/poverty-children
Q4.A	How many HMO licenses were in force, and how much urban vacant land was there in East Ayrshire in 2016? Reference datasets: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/hmo-licences , http://statistics.gov.scot/data/settlements-and-localities-population
Q4.B	How much urban vacant land was there in East Ayrshire, and how many Scottish Child Payment applications were denied for individuals aged 25-50 in Scotland in 2014? Reference datasets: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/area-improvement-shs , http://statistics.gov.scot/data/settlements-and-localities-population
Q4.C	In Scotland in 2014, what were the amount and ratio of incidents of domestic abuse recorded per 10,000 population, and what were the index value and annual growth rate of goods and services produced in the construction sector (Section F)? Reference datasets: https://statistics.gov.scot/data/new-build-housing-starts-and-completions , http://statistics.gov.scot/data/perceptions-of-local-crime-rate-sscq
Q4.D	What percentage of children were classed as overweight, and how many operating sites were there in Scotland in 2018? Reference datasets: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/scottish-health-survey-scotland-level-data , http://statistics.gov.scot/data/scottish-health-survey-local-area-level-data
Q4.E	In Scotland in 2014, what were the count, ratio, 95% upper confidence limit, and 95% lower confidence limit for unemployment model-based estimates across all industry sectors, and what were the median, mean, lower quartile, and upper quartile values of residential property transactions? Reference datasets: http://statistics.gov.scot/data/shqs , http://statistics.gov.scot/data/new-build-housing-starts-and-completions

Table 1: Question pool of the framework. The IDs of the questions are of the form QX.Y, where X is the category and Y the number of the questions among the category.

Figure 2: System workflow

successfully identified the correct set of measures. This outcome is not surprising, given that the labels of measures in the questions closely align with those provided by the datasets’ codelists. The measure labels are inherently consistent because they refer to well-defined concepts. For instance, a measure like *95% upper confidence limit* is likely to appear similarly in the question. Similarly, a measure described as *q-on-q* might be written out as *quarter-on-quarter*, which is sufficiently similar to the reference, making it easier for LLMs to interpret and match accurately. In Figure 3, correct results are highlighted in green, while incorrect results are marked in red. Results shown in orange indicate outputs that, although not perfectly aligned with the ground truth, could still be utilized within a complete system with additional filtering and post-processing steps.

For the Dataset Selection task, we also tested the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 as a smaller, more efficient alternative due to the task’s lower complexity and reduced reasoning requirements. However, the larger models consistently outperformed the smaller one across all categories, making it unsuitable for our use case. In Figure 3 we present the results for the three bigger models. In Category 1, all larger models struggled with question *Q1.C* due to the word *“applications”*. This word appears on both the question and the description of the retrieved dataset. The description of the correct dataset, while similar, does not contain this specific word, potentially leading to confusion. For Category 2, Llama successfully retrieved all relevant datasets, whereas the other two models struggled with question *Q2.D*. A similar issue was observed here: the term *“unemployment”* seemed to create embeddings that led to mismatches in Mistral and Gemma’s retrieval processes. In Category 3, all models succeeded across all questions. It was noted that in this category, the descriptions of the correct datasets closely matched the terminology used in the questions, contributing to the models’ success. In contrast,

for Category 4, all models failed to retrieve the correct datasets for every question. While were able to identify one of the two relevant datasets, they were unable to retrieve the second one.

Regarding the *Dimension Value Extraction* task we observe that for Category 1 Llama, although gives satisfying responds in general, for questions *Q2.B*, *Q2.C* and *Q2.E* fails to extract a value for one dimension per question, returning empty string. Mistral and Gemma missed *Q2.C* and *Q2.B* respectively. Both gave wrong values for one dimension per question. In category 2 all models responded correctly on all questions. This is logical as the questions in this category are focused on multiple measures with less dimensions mentioned in the question. Category 3 gives the most interesting results. Llama proves to handle all questions, finding both the correct values but also the dimensions without a value in the question. In contrast, the other two models while they find the existing values, they tend to hallucinate when it comes to dimensions without a value present in the question. For example, for questions with the dimension *“Reference Period”* not specified, both Mistral and Gemma tend to respond with random dates. Another common response for unspecified values is the phrase *“Not specified”*. This value while erroneous, can be easily filtered out in next steps. Particularly, Gemma hallucinates for every question. In Category 4, all models successfully handled three questions, with some responses being considered acceptable despite not being entirely accurate. However, both Mistral and Gemma produced unusable responses for two of the questions.

All models demonstrated strong performance in the *Final Response Generation* task. They handled the JSON responds from the portal and produced human readable outputs. Neither of the models gave hallucinated responses or shown other over-generation errors. For questions where a large number of dimension values was not specified, the volume of the portal’s response data was larger

Figure 3: Results for the Dataset Selection (left bar) and Dimension Value Extraction (right bar) tasks. Correct results are highlighted in green, while incorrect results are marked in red. Orange represents partially correct results.

than average. Even in these cases, the models accurately addressed all the relevant details presented in the data, producing comprehensive responses. Although some of the outputs were dense, the information was conveyed correctly and thoroughly.

In general, Llama proved to handle the multitude of tasks and questions better than the other models. What distinguishes its performance is the fact that it was able to identify measures with no values mentioned in the question. In those cases it responded with empty strings for the unspecified measures, as intended. Also, Llama was the only model without overgeneration mistakes.

8 Discussion and conclusion

In this study we proposed a framework for assessing the performance of Large Language Models (LLMs) in the specific context of accessing linked Open Government Data (OGD). The framework consists of a pool of 20 questions classified into four categories. These questions are derived from the structure of the Scottish Open Statistical Portal available datasets and their categories are determined by the properties of linked data and the QB vocabulary. Three LLMs were integrated into a simple implementation that provides basic functionalities supporting interaction with the OGD of the portal. We also propose an experimental setup testing LLMs within four tasks *Dataset Selection*, *Measure Selection*, *Dimension Value Extraction* and *Final Response Generation*.

Within our implementation LLMs are tested on four tasks, *Dataset Selection*, *Measure Selection*, *Dimension Value Extraction* and *Final*

Response Generation. While this work being specified to one case study, interacting with OGD, the tasks value selection and extraction, dataset selection and generation are of general purpose. So our results could be used to further understand the abilities of LLMs in general. The three bigger models proved to have strong reasoning abilities when it comes to select the correct measure label and extract the correct dimension values, with mistral-7b-instruct-v0.3-bnb-4bit and gemma-2-9b-bnb-4bit tending to hallucinate when values are not specified for each dimension, with Gemma hallucinating in every such case.

Overall, Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct-bnb-4bit emerged as the most effective model across all tasks, making it a good candidate to be included in the implementation of such systems. What stands out, is its ability to correctly identify and handle cases where values for each dimension are not specified. It responds with an empty string for these dimensions without over-generation faults. Another important aspect that our results identify is the fact that the 4bit quantized versions of relatively small Language Models performed well on multiple tasks that require reasoning abilities. This opens the way to implement systems that automate tasks such as creating SPARQL queries to access public data.

Another aspect that the results of our study revealed is the need for a robust framework for linked data. There have been efforts to bring upfront problems that arise from insufficient interoperability present in currently created ontologies [14]. Although efforts have

been made to tackle existing shortcomings [16], especially when it comes to large scale applications that rely on such systems.

As part of our future work, we aim to develop a comprehensive system that functions as an interface between users and the Scottish Open Statistical Portal. Similar systems have relied heavily on private models to implement their functionalities [20]. However, based on the findings of this study, it seems feasible to design a more versatile system leveraging smaller open-source models. This system will incorporate LLMs for the tasks outlined in this study, supported by additional functionalities that handle input processing and refine the outputs generated by the LLMs. This integration will create a more robust and user-friendly interface, enhancing overall user interaction with the statistical data.

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